

REVISITING THE END USER'S PERSPECTIVE IN COLLABORATIVE HUMAN-ROBOT INTERACTION

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The disciplines of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) have evolved rather independently since their early days, mainly because early computers and early robots shared little common ground. However, as computers have jumped off the desktop to pervade the physical world, and as robots extend themselves from the physical world into the cloud, traditional boundaries between these two technological entities have blurred out due to the increasing complexity of their natural habitats. In this paper, we take a snapshot of these converging evolutions, and enquire about the benefits that the human user in HRI can derive from applying HCI methods for R&D, including viewing the collaborative robot itself as an interface.

1. Introduction

By definition, the disciplines of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) share the common element of a *human actor*. Around that human actor (i.e., a person, end user of the technology), there is a *computer* in the first case and a *robot* in the second. The human actor *interacts* with each one of these technologies in order to achieve certain *goals*, which in turn dictate *requirements* that the technology has to satisfy.

The elements outlined in the paragraph above, constitute the foundational framework on top of which these two disciplines of study (HCI and HRI) operate, centered on the end user's needs and goals. Interaction designers that contribute to HCI, HRI or both, have the role to design, test and propose new interaction techniques that best serve the end user's needs and task requirements when interacting with computers or robots. With their designs, they outline roadmaps for technology developers to produce new enablers needed in their envisioned interactions, and their work is fueled by advances in enabling technologies that make it to the labs and to the market. When made available, such enablers are

Figure 1. Converging evolution of HCI and HRI around the human end user

implemented across the board on technology-based systems and devices (including robotic systems), intended for any kind of user and use scenario. In contrast, the human factors taken into account are often dependent on whether the system is a computer or a robot, a personal consumer device or a productivity-oriented industrial system. This is due to the fact that HCI and HRI are the result of different traditions that originated from distant initial points (early computers and robots were very different animals), which have evolved through rather independent paths towards the current common scenario around the end user (Figure 1).

In this paper, we focus on the convergence point of the evolution paths that HCI and HRI have followed. We do so from the perspective of the interaction with collaborative robots (COBOTS), which should occupy that convergence point. As part of the H2020 FourByThree* project, we propose that considering the robot itself as the interface can help COBOTS claim that convergence point

* <http://fourbythree.eu/>

between disciplines, while supporting a truly collaborative relationship between a person and a robot that share the same task in the same workspace.

In the following sections, we outline the main milestones that have led to this convergence of disciplines. We then make a case for the concept of user experience (UX) in HRI, as a metric originated from HCI that should be central in the development of the robot-as-interface concept.

2. The converging evolutions of HCI and HRI

Computers and robots are immersed in an ongoing fast-paced train of transformation, and both HCI and HRI are constantly adapting to changes in technology. The ever-further miniaturization of digital electronics has democratized computational capacity. Benefiting from that, disciplines such as data science, artificial intelligence, and materials science, are providing engineers and designers with algorithms, hardware solutions, and exotic new sensors that are driving the evolution of everything computerized around us, including robots. As a result, a technological convergence has taken place between computers and robots, making it increasingly difficult to differentiate them from the perspective of human-technology interaction. Reviewing each of these paths of evolution can help with understanding these differences and identifying opportunities.

2.1. *The evolution of HCI*

The main stem of mainstream HCI emerged from the use of the very first digital computers. With the advent of the Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) and Direct Manipulation [1], the Desktop Metaphor got consolidated as the dominant interaction paradigm. For a long time, psychologists were first in studying the human part of HCI, and they focused heavily on the study of visual perception and cognition, attention and memory. From that time, research methods from psychology became the norm in HCI research. In those visual-display-centric systems, InfoVis (the discipline that studies the visual representation of information) [2], found fertile ground for its development via rich interactive visualizations on computer displays. Later on, but already nearly three decades ago, multimodal interfaces incorporated new sensory channels to the development of new interactions that made a broader use of the person's perceptual and cognitive capacities. Around the same time, auditory displays [3] studied new forms of complex data representations that were intrinsically non-visual. Haptic interfaces experienced a rapid development in areas such as force feedback, with which remote or virtual objects could really be felt with the hands [4]. This marked, within HCI, the beginning of embodied interactions with the physical

(albeit virtualized) world. The evolution of multimodality brought about the first Virtual Reality systems (VR) [5], and later on the more demanding Augmented Reality (AR) ones [6], in which the user consumed and interacted with a fusion of real and computer-generated data that were linked to the physical environment around the user. It is only in recent years that the enabling technologies have reached maturity for the mainstream adoption of VR and AR.

Mobility, and more recently wearability, of personal computers freed the computer user from his desk, allowing for interactions anywhere and on the go, through the use of new mobile interaction techniques. Mobile HCI gave a more prominent role to research methods that were better suited to evaluations in the field and in social contexts, rather than within the lab [7]. Thus, disciplines such as ethnography and sociology contributed their well-established research methods to the corpus of methods used in HCI. Almost paradoxically, the desktop metaphor still sticks around (e.g., in smartphone operating systems), and mobile interfaces have remained stubbornly vision-centric. Auditory interfaces are only testimonial and relegated to fancy alarms, and haptic experiences have been reduced to minimalistic expressions.

Two strands in HCI have recently shown significant development towards overcoming the WIMP (Windows, Icons, Menus, Pointer) [8] legacy. First, with research methods from linguistics and through new machine-learning-based enablers, interfaces based on natural language are reaching enough maturity through semantic technologies [9] to partially free the user's vision and support multitasking. Second, a trend for physically-rich interfaces in the form of physical user interfaces (such as tangibles [10], deformable computers [11, 12], and the physicalizations of information [13]), which bring new prominence to the physical properties of the interface. Thus, interfaces are objects that increasingly live in the three-dimensional physical space, together with the humans that use them, in the same way physical robots do.

2.2. The evolution of HRI

The statement in this paper that HCI and HRI have converged into a common ground of interaction with the human actor, has already been shown in the previous paragraph. In it, the description of the later stages in the evolution of HCI lists current interaction trends and enabling technologies that receive just as much attention from HRI in its latest developments. This is coherent with the fact that both computers and robots have come to occupy the same physical space and the same distributed connectivity (i.e., the same space in the cloud).

Considering the evolution of interaction through the prism of industrial HRI, in the beginning there was not a common physical space for interaction between a person and an active robot, primarily for safety reasons [14]. The interaction between them was limited to the programming phase, and even then, it was mediated by desktop human-computer interfaces. Later on, robots evolved senses that made them aware of their environment (machine vision, proximity and contact sensing). With improved and additional sensing, robots became reliable in identifying human presence in their space of action, and Human-Robot Interaction gained a new meaning in terms of collaboration in the same physical space (COBOTS) [15]. From that point on, sociability became an element of paramount importance for safety and collaborative productivity. Currently, some of the challenges for interaction design with collaborative robots lie on providing the human partner with situational awareness about the robot, its state, how it is interpreting the collaborative context, and anticipation of its immediate future actions [16]. In the collaborative relationship between the person and the robot, the skill of the robot to keep its human partner informed can be seen as an etiquette requirement without which the user has to maintain taxing levels of extra-vigilance for execution mistakes or even risk situations that might arise at any point. However, even when the robot can perform its physical tasks well, and is aware of (and respectful with) human presence sharing the same workspace, it struggles keeping that same human actor aware of its own understanding of the situation and of its imminent action plans.

3. In the point of convergence: the robot as an interface

HRI arrives at the point of convergence with many and sound legacy strengths in physical manipulation and contact interaction with humans in the 3D space, assisted by advanced sensing and interpretation of the environment, and with tested collision-safety standards. In turn, HCI brings to the point of convergence important complementary contributions that assist technology in embracing the end user. One contribution stands out in particular: the well-established concept of *User Experience* (UX). Applied to robotics, UX is the result of a holistic assessment of the objective and subjective imprint left on the end user by every aspect surrounding the relationship between the person and the robot. When this relationship is collaborative, aspects that are likely to influence the outcome in a UX assessment will include the efficiency and effectiveness of the collaboration, safety and perception of safety, overall workload, fluency of interaction, ergonomics and aesthetics, among a longer list.

As mentioned above, if the robot struggles to keep its human partner ‘in the loop’, aware of its intentions for immediate action and about its understanding of the course of the collaboration, the end user develops a sense of uncertainty, which damages the end user’s experience (her UX). Surprise and unexpected movements are at the root of the majority of accidents with robots [17, 18]. Even when robots are deemed safe for collaboration, research shows that less experienced users tend to be extra-vigilant and weary of the action decisions and action executions of robots, which has the counter-productive effect of stealing attention resources from the end user for vigilance and supervision, rather than freeing them for true parallel collaborative work [19]. In practice, there is a shared level of uncertainty between robot and person in the moments that precede the robot’s actions. The person is uncertain about whether the robot will fulfil the actions expected from it, or even if it will perform any actions at all. On the robot’s side, there is a level of uncertainty in the action decisions that it takes, which originates from the ambiguity of the user’s instructions and from the uncertainty of the algorithms that have led to taking those decisions [20, 21]. Learning from HCI, the negative effect that uncertainty can have on UX can be reduced if the end user can refer to an interface that (i) keeps the user informed of what is going on in the system, and (ii) allows the user to cancel or modify ongoing processes or actions, thus granting him an enhanced sense of control [22].

As discussed earlier, for a truly collaborative interaction with a robot in the same workspace, we propose that the robot itself is the interface. For this purpose, the robot’s embodiment is required to include (i) a display with real-time information about the robot’s confidence and understanding of the status of the interaction, plus its plans for immediate action, and (ii) an input device to modify, modulate or cancel altogether the robot’s next actions. This display and input device have to merge naturally with the interaction flow during collaboration. The goal is that they provide a level of naturalness comparable with instructing the robot via spoken language and deictic gestures. As an important additional requirement, the robot being the interface should not increase the cognitive workload, but it should free mental and perceptual resources in an end user that does not have to monitor the robot so closely due to uncertainty.

As also mentioned, the H2020 FourByThree project is taking steps towards contributing to this goal. As examples of input modalities on the robot, the project is investigating natural input techniques such as hand guiding, voice input using natural language, plus pointing gestures. Semantic technologies are being employed on the robot side in order to obtain a coherent fusion of the complementary input information that arrives simultaneously from these input channels. As an example of output on the robot interface, the FourByThree project

is investigating the use of projection systems that outline the perimeter of action of the robot for safety purposes, and can be used for interaction and visualization. In fact, it is possible to visualize relevant information to support the worker's task and also provide virtual buttons or simple menus that the worker can use to control the robot. As future steps, we will follow a user-centered methodology inspired by interface design practices from HCI. The process will include the capture of requirements, the identification of perceptual, cognitive and physical resources available from the user, and iterative design, validation and evaluation cycles.

4. Conclusions

The converging evolutions of HCI and HRI have met in interactive scenarios that share important commonalities: the end user utilizes technology in the physical space and with physical actions, while technology monitors and strives to understand the end user, with the help of sensors and pervading cloud connectivity. Relatively recent collaborative robots can benefit from the use of HCI design methods that seek to model the end user's UX, by improving feedback communication and improving situational awareness in the user. We propose that viewing the collaborative robot itself as an interface can accommodate natural input and output techniques that can ease uncertainty, grant control through anticipation, and improve the outcome of collaborative tasks, including the user's reported UX.

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